

Number:

Date:

Farm Data

Name of farm:

Address:

Federal state:

Registration number:

Phone Number:

- Trial group:
 - Reproductive problems + tetracycline
 - Reproductive problems without tetracycline
- Number of sows:
- Genetics:
- Farm type:
 - Conventional
 - Organic
 - Farrow-to-finish farm
 - Piglet producer

1. Farm management

- Batch farrowing rhythm
 - 3 weeks
 - 4 weeks
 - Other.....
- Weaning day
 - Mon
 - Tue
 - Wed
 - Thu
 - Fri
 - Sat
 - Sun
- Main breeding day
 - Mon
 - Tue
 - Wed
 - Thu
 - Fri
 - Sat
 - Sun
- How often are sows inseminated on average per estrus?
- Is hormonal induction of birth performed?
 - Yes.....
 - No

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- Source of gilts
 - Gilts born and raised on farm
 - gilts from an external source
 - Other.....

- Measures taken for quarantine
 - Own pen, same barn and air space as herd
 - Own pen, separate air space
 - Own stable = own pen in another building
 - No quarantine

- Number of days of quarantine:.....

2. Breeding

- Teasing boar on duty?
 - Yes: age of boar.....
 - no

- Origin of sperm
 - Boar stud
 - Other external source (e.g. neighbor)
 - Breeding boar
 - Natural breeding; age...
 - Artificial insemination; age.....

- How many persons do perform artificial insemination?.....
- Temperate sperm cabin?
 - Yes
 - No

- Does the vulva get cleaned before artificial insemination?
 - Yes wet, water only
 - Yes wet, water + cleaning agent
 - Yes dry
 - no

- Which artificial insemination method is used?
 - Intrauterine
 - Intracervical (catheter with yellow head)

- Is the insemination catheter used more than once?
 - Yes.....
 - No

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3. Health data and general problems

- Most common health problem on the farm (not fertility related)
.....

- Does conjunctivitis occur frequently on the farm/is it treated?
 - No
 - In sows
 - In suckling piglets
 - In nursery piglets
 - In fattening pigs
 - Boars

- Replacement of sows
 - Replacement rate (%).....
 - Sows culled/year.....
 - Most common reason for culling.....
 - Average age/number of litters at culling.....

- Name of slaughterhouse, where sows are culled
.....

- For which animals is estrus hormonally induced?
 - None
 - Gilts
 - Sows
 - Animals with reproductive problems
 - All

- Which hormonal treatment protocol is used?
 - No synchronization
 - FSH/LH administration after weaning
 - Synchronization with Altrenogest
 - Synchronization with Altrenogest + FSH/LH

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4. Reproductive performance data:

! Have sow planner handed out!

Sow performance data of last 12 months

- Farrowing rate %.....
- Return-to-estrus rate %.....
- Abortion rate %.....
- Number of non-productive-days.....
- Litters/sow/year.....
- Total number of piglets born/sow/litter.....
- Number of piglets born alive/sow/litter.....
- Number of weaned piglets/sow/litter.....
- Stillborn rate %.....
- Mummies %.....
- Gilts/sows differences if available

5. Reproductive problems:

- What is the main reproductive problem?
 - Abortions
 - Increase of Return-to-estrus rate
 - PPDS
 - SMEDI
 - Vaginal discharge
 - Other.....

- How many sows show vaginal discharge after farrowing:%
- Description of discharge
 - Purulent
 - Mucous
 - Smelly
 - Reddish/brown

- Which parities (number of litters) are affected?
 - 1
 - 2
 - 3-5
 - 6-9
 - >9
 - Varies

- Is inner body temperature routinely measured in sows after farrowing?
 - Yes
 - No

- How many sows have an increased temperature after farrowing?..... %
- How many sows show PPDS after birth..... %

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6. Diagnostics

- Which samples have been taken for diagnostics of reproductive problems?
 - Abortion material
 - Genital swabs
 - Blood samples
 - None

- Results of the diagnostics carried out?
 - None
 -

- Which diagnostics specific for *Chlamydia suis* have been performed?
 - None
 - Direct detection of antigen via PCR
 - Material?.....
 - Indirect via antibody detection in blood samples
 - Other.....

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7. Use of medication and vaccinations

- PRRS status
 - Unsuspicious
 - Positive

8. Vaccination of pigs against reproductive disorders

Pathogene	Gilts	Sows	Vaccine
PRRS			
Porcine Parvovirus			
Erysipelas			
Leptospirosis			
Influenza A			
PCV2-RD			

Metaphylactic antibiotic treatment

- Are antibiotics regularly administered to all animals or individual groups?
 - No metaphylactic antibiotic treatment at herd/group level
 - To the whole herd
 - To individual sow groups (e.g. during breeding)

Which treatment protocol was followed?

- Intervals
 - time based, e.g. 2x/year
 - Production-based, e.g. breeding batch
 - Other.....
- Method of administration
 - Feed
 - Drinking water
 - Other.....
- Name of the preparation.....
- Dose/concentration.....
- Number of days of administration:

Therapies

- Therapy for PPDS
 - Medications:.....
 - Duration of application.....
 - Dose.....
 - Application method.....
- How are acute reproductive problems treated?
.....
- How long are antibiotics used?
 - No antibiotics used for fertility problems
 - Number of days:.....
- Application?
 - Orally
 - Intramuscularly
- Who is treated?
 - Individual animals
 - Sow batches
 - Whole herd

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9. Biosecurity, animal flow and other

- Do other animals have access to the barn
 - No
 - Cats
 - Dogs
 - Small ruminants
 - Cattle
 - Other.....

- Other animals on the farm?
 - No, only pigs on the farm
 - Cats
 - Dogs
 - Cows
 - Small ruminants
 - Horses
 - Other.....

- Is there a problem with rodents/birds etc.?
 - Birds
 - Rats
 - Mice
 - Excessive flies

10. Cleaning/disinfection in general, but especially in the breeding room and farrowing pen:

- Are sows washed before farrowing?
 - Yes.....
 - No

- All-in/all-out is implemented in which areas?
 - Nowhere on the farm
 - Farrowing pen
 - Gestation pen
 - Breeding pen
 - Quarantine room
 - Piglet area

- Cleaning of farrowing pen
 - How is cleaning done (water, soap, etc)
 - Cleaning with a high-pressure washer?
 - Disinfectant.....
 - How long is farrowing room left empty between groups....
 - Exposure time of disinfectant.....
 -

- Cleaning of gestation pen:
 - How is cleaning done (water, soap, etc)
 - Cleaning with a high-pressure washer?
 - Disinfectant.....
 - How long is gestation pen left empty between groups...
 - Exposure time of disinfectant.....

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- Description of the entrance area:
 - Showering mandatory for external persons (vet)
 -

- Do weaned piglets have contact with sows via driveways or similar?
 - Yes.....
 - No

- Are separate shoes used for different areas
 - Yes.....
 - No

11. Notes:

Cleanlines, washing rooms, Change of shoes between piglets and sows, animal contact, production areas?

Overcrowding e.g. in nursery